

CLEWs-Based Power Sector Scenarios for Lowering CO₂e_q Emissions in Brazil

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This study investigates the implications of adopting an integrated systems approach for power technology transitions in Brazil, focusing on climate, land, energy, and water systems. Through modelling exercises utilising the CLEWs framework and OSeMOSYS tool, three scenarios - Baseline, Balance, and Renew - were developed to assess their impact on emissions, land and water demand.

Findings reveal that while the Renew scenario, driven by renewable energy sources, achieves the lowest emissions rates and water demand, it also exhibits the highest land use associated with biofuel production. The study emphasises the importance of considering water and land demand as costs comparable to CO₂ emissions in assessing the cost perspective of power technology transitions.

Recommendations include integrating water and land management policies into energy planning, prioritising investments in renewable energy sources with lower water and land footprints and exploring the potential of different technologies to meet energy and climate demands while minimising carbon emissions and environmental impacts.

INTRODUCTION

As the 7th largest global energy consumer and the largest in South America, Brazil holds significant sway over regional energy dynamics. Additionally, it boasts a prominent position as a major oil and gas producer, coupled with the distinction of being the world's second-largest ethanol fuel producer. Brazil's abundant land, water, and energy resources provide a fertile ground for energy exploration and innovation. Amidst these opportunities, the country faces a critical environmental challenge, as the primary source of its greenhouse gas emissions stems from deforestation for agricultural purposes (Climate Policy Initiative, 2023). This complex interplay of factors underscores the importance of understanding how different scenarios of power technology transitions may impact emissions, land and water demand within Brazil's socio-economic and environmental context.

This study explores the implications of adopting an integrated systems approach for power technology transitions in Brazil, with a specific focus on climate, land, energy, and water systems. The purpose is to assess how different scenarios, ranging from baseline reliance on natural gas to a transition towards 100% renewable energy sources, affect emissions, land and water demand, and cost perspectives. The scope of the study is to perform a comparative analysis of three scenarios - Baseline, Balance, and Renew - using the CLEWs framework within the OSeMOSYS tool.

The primary objective is to understand how the adoption of an integrated systems approach alters the cost perspective of power technology transitions in Brazil. This analysis also aims to evaluate the impact of different scenarios on emissions, land and water demand, and provide insights and recommendations for policymakers and stakeholders in the energy sector. By examining these scenarios within Brazil's context, this study seeks to contribute to the ongoing discourse on sustainable energy transitions and climate mitigation strategies.

METHODOLOGY

In this research, the CLEWs (Climate, Land, Energy, and Water Systems) framework was applied using the OSeMOSYS (Open Source Energy Modelling System) tool. While OSeMOSYS was originally developed for energy systems analysis, its functionality and flexibility permit its adaptation to the integrated analysis of CLEWs. This approach facilitates a comprehensive assessment of the interactions and interdependencies among climate, land, energy, and water systems, enabling a whole systems approach to decision-making (Ramos et al., 2022).

The Starter Data Kit (SDK) provided within the OSeMOSYS toolkit for Brazil served as the baseline model, incorporating the reference energy system developed by Cannone and Allington (2021). Additionally, agriculture and water data were sourced from Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), and International Energy Agency (IEA) databases.

Three scenarios were developed: Baseline, Balance, and Renew. The **Baseline** scenario represents the current state with no policy or resource constraints. The **Balance** scenario introduces annual emission limits aligned with Brazil's Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs). The **Renew** scenario aims for a net-zero power sector by 2050, with higher renewable energy adoption and restricted fossil fuel usage.

Figure 1: Summary of Scenarios' Key Assumptions

The CLEWs modelling methodology allowed for an analysis of technology-specific challenges and their implications for energy policy decision-making. While the long-term vision remains integrated and considers multiple energy supply alternatives, the approach focused on cost optimisation outcomes under emission and technology constraints. The study did not aim to re-examine challenges associated with technological development, cost evolution, or support for research and development. Instead, it aimed to identify challenges where energy sector authorities could directly or collaboratively engage with other sectors to achieve the country's climate goals.

RESULTS

This modelling exercise explored the following research question:

How does adopting an integrated systems approach alter the cost perspective of power technology transitions in Brazil?

Results revealed distinct trajectories across the three scenarios: Baseline, Balance, and Renew, each shedding light on critical facets of the transition:

- In the **Baseline** scenario, natural gas emerges as a primary player in power production, necessitating the lowest capital investment yet yielding the highest emissions rates.
- The **Balance** scenario witnesses a gradual integration of biofuels, accompanied by a 30% surge in capital investment and emissions peaking before stabilising.
- The **Renew** scenario, marked by a significant uptake of biofuels and wind power, demands the highest capital investment but boasts the lowest emissions rates, aligning with Brazil's Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) for the power sector by 2050.

Figure 2: Power Generation Capacity in Three Scenarios

The examination of CO₂-equivalent emissions across the three scenarios shows distinct trajectories and implications for climate mitigation within the power sector.

In the **Baseline** scenario, total emissions remain notably high throughout the analysis period. This elevated emission level is primarily attributed to the substantial use of fossil fuels, particularly oil, gas, and coal, for power generation. The Baseline scenario reflects a business-as-usual approach, highlighting the relevance of alternative strategies to curb emissions and align with global climate goals.

The **Balance** scenario presents a shift towards biofuel and renewable power generation, aiming to align emissions with climate targets. While this transition contributes to a moderate decrease in emissions compared to the Baseline scenario, emissions remain notably higher than those projected in the Renew scenario. This exemplifies the complexity of balancing emissions reduction objectives with the need to maintain energy security and affordability.

In the **Renew** scenario, characterised by a progressive transition towards renewable energy sources, total emissions exhibit a substantial decrease across the entire analysis period. This scenario achieves the lowest emissions rate among the three scenarios, aligning closely with Brazil's climate objectives and demonstrating the potential of renewable energy to drive significant emissions reductions within the power sector.

Figure 4: Total Emissions by Scenario

Exploring the performance of the three scenarios regarding carbon emissions and further delving into land and water dynamics unveils important insights into the balance between mitigating CO₂-equivalent emissions and optimising resource utilisation within the power sector. Particularly noteworthy is the diverse impact of renewable energy

sources on water and land demand, with biofuel production exerting the most significant influence.

As shown in Figure 3, in the **Baseline** scenario, characterised by a heavy reliance on natural gas, the demand for water remains substantial, primarily driven by the need for cooling thermal power plants. This reliance on water-intensive power generation methods underscores the inherent trade-off between meeting energy demands and minimising water consumption, highlighting the challenge of sustainable resource management.

The **Balance** scenario introduces a shift towards biofuel and renewable power generation, aiming to align emissions with Brazil's Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs). While this transition contributes to a moderate decrease in water demand compared to the Baseline scenario, it still requires a considerable level of water usage, particularly for cooling purposes.

In the **Renew** scenario, characterised by a progressive transition towards renewable energy sources, the demand for water experiences a notable reduction compared to the Baseline and Balance scenarios. However, this scenario also witnesses a significant increase in land use associated with biofuel production. This points to the importance of striking a balance between transitioning to lower-emission power sources and managing land resources sustainably.

Figure 3: Power Sector Water Demand and Land Use by Scenario

DISCUSSION

The local context plays a pivotal role in shaping climate pathways, with the availability and demand for land, water, and energy emerging as critical factors influencing cost-benefit options. Brazil, as the world's second largest ethanol fuel producer, stands at the forefront of contributing technological solutions to climate ambitions. While the country possesses significant potential in this regard, it is important to consider the

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impact of water and land use on technology development demands and the balanced expansion of this solution within the energy matrix.

Natural Gas, a major player in Brazil's energy balance and international trade, holds strategic importance. The gas regulator, ANP (Agência Nacional de Petróleo), advocates for further exploration of reserves, sparking discussions about the feasibility of utilising natural gas for low-carbon hydrogen production, particularly when coupled with Carbon Capture, Utilisation, and Storage (CCUS) technologies. This scenarios exercise reveals that, from a climate perspective, natural gas may prove attractive due to its relatively lower land requirements for production.

This analysis provides practical perspectives into the cost-effectiveness of strategies aimed at reducing water and land footprints, where impact on water and land is considered as a cost. Most importantly, it emphasises the strategic role of water and land in advancing climate objectives within and beyond the power sector.

The Climate, Land, Energy, and Water Systems (CLEWs) approach to integrated systems management emerges as a valuable tool, offering a holistic analysis that extends beyond climate considerations to encompass the integration of energy, land and water systems. This whole systems perspective becomes especially pertinent as these systems are inherently interconnected, highlighting the importance of considering their collective impact.

It is also important to acknowledge the limitations that apply to this exercise, which relies on a simplified reference energy system (RES) for Brazil. The model, while informative, does not encompass the full spectrum of energy, land and water systems. Consequently, the insights developed offer a partial view of the implications and potentials associated with different pathways. Recognising these constraints leads to opportunities of future research that builds upon this foundation, expanding the model to provide a more faithful representation of Brazil's complex energy, land and water systems.

Potential areas for further research include representation of technologies such as Hydrogen, Nuclear and CCUS and an analysis of their influence over the country's energy options. Expanding the scope to explore ambitions for land and water use, industrial and transportation transitions, among others, will contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the dynamics at play. In addition, integrating scenario outcomes with complementary CCG tools such as MARIO for value chain analysis holds promise for exploring the social risks and opportunities associated with technology choices, providing an even more comprehensive for decision-making.

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CONCLUSION

This study has explored the interplay between power technology transitions and energy, land and water systems in Brazil. By analysing three scenarios - Baseline, Balance, and Renew - this research has gleaned insights into the potential implications of adopting an integrated systems approach. Findings underscore the importance of considering water and land demand as critical components in assessing the cost perspective of power technology transitions.

Moving forward, it is recommended that policymakers and stakeholders in the energy sector to prioritise investments in renewable energy sources with lower environmental footprints while exploring innovative solutions to mitigate the impact of deforestation on greenhouse gas emissions. By embracing a systemic approach that integrates energy, land and water considerations, Brazil can pave the way for a more sustainable and resilient climate future.

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